

MSR2025_RQ1

November 24, 2024

1 Mining Software Repositories(MSR) 2025 - Mining Challenge

2 Research Question #1 (RQ1)

Can we deduce the different clusters from the Maven Central's dependency graph, and how do these clusters interact with one another?

3 Cluster Identification

3.0.1 Query Setup

```
[2]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import networkx as nx
import json
import os
import seaborn as sns
```

```
[3]: # Increase the width to avoid content wrapping
pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None) # Set to 'None' to avoid truncation
pd.set_option('display.width', 1000) # Increase the display width (adjust
↳based on your needs)
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None) # Display all columns in the
↳dataframe
```

```
[6]: from neo4j import GraphDatabase

#connect to the database
uri = "bolt://localhost:7687"
driver = GraphDatabase.driver(uri, auth=("neo4j", "Password1"))
```

```
[8]: def execute_query(query, parameters=None):
    with driver.session() as session:
        result = session.run(query, parameters or {})
        return result.data()
```

```
[10]: gds_version = """
CALL gds.version()
"""

print(execute_query(gds_version))
```

```
[{'gdsVersion': '2.6.8'}]
```

3.0.2 Create Projected Graph

Ensure the Graph is Fully Projected

The entire Maven Repository graph, including all Artifact and Release nodes

```
[13]: # Fetch all node property keys from the database
property_keys_query = """
CALL db.propertyKeys() YIELD propertyKey
RETURN collect(propertyKey) AS propertyKeys
"""

result = execute_query(property_keys_query)
property_keys = result[0]['propertyKeys']
print(f"Node property keys: {property_keys}")
```

```
Node property keys: ['id', 'found', 'version', 'timestamp', 'scope',
'targetVersion', 'type', 'value', 'communityId']
```

```
[16]: # Define the graph name
graph_name = 'mavenGraph'

# Check if the graph exists and drop it if it does
graph_exists_query = f"""
CALL gds.graph.exists('{graph_name}')
YIELD exists
"""

exists_result = execute_query(graph_exists_query)
if exists_result and exists_result[0]['exists']:
    drop_graph_query = f"""
CALL gds.graph.drop('{graph_name}')
YIELD graphName
"""

    execute_query(drop_graph_query)
    print(f"Existing graph '{graph_name}' has been dropped.")

# Project the graph without node properties
graph_projection_query = f"""
CALL gds.graph.project(
    '{graph_name}',
    ['Artifact', 'Release'],
    {{
        dependency: {{
```

```

        orientation: 'UNDIRECTED'
    }},
    relationship_AR: [{
        orientation: 'UNDIRECTED'
    }]
    }]
)
"""
execute_query(graph_projection_query)
print(f"Graph '{graph_name}' has been projected into GDS.")

```

Graph 'mavenGraph' has been projected into GDS.

3.0.3 Checking Graph

List node properties in the graph

```

[19]: # Query to list node properties in the graph
node_properties_query = f"""
CALL db.labels()
"""
node_properties = execute_query(node_properties_query)
print("Node Properties:")
for row in node_properties:
    print(row)

```

```

Node Properties:
{'label': 'Artifact'}
{'label': 'Release'}
{'label': 'AddedValue'}

```

3.0.4 Previously Saved Algorithms

```

[21]: leiden_results_file = 'Leiden_algorithm_results.json'

```

3.1 Leiden

3.1.1 Running the Leiden Algorithm

```

[28]: # Run the Leiden algorithm
leiden_algorithm_query = f"""
CALL gds.leiden.mutate('{graph_name}', [{
    mutateProperty: 'communityId'
}])
YIELD communityCount, modularity
"""
leiden_results = execute_query(leiden_algorithm_query)
print(f"Leiden algorithm completed. Number of communities found: {
    ↪{leiden_results[0]['communityCount']}")

```

```
Leiden algorithm completed. Number of communities found: 67669
```

3.1.2 Save Results for Future Analysis

```
[31]: with open('Leiden_algorithm_results.json','w') as json_file:
      json.dump(leiden_results, json_file)
      print("Leiden algorithm results saved to 'Leiden_algorithm_results.json'")
```

```
Leiden algorithm results saved to 'Leiden_algorithm_results.json'
```

3.1.3 Retrieve Saved Results

```
[34]: with open('Leiden_algorithm_results.json', 'r') as json_file:
      leiden_cluster_results = json.load(json_file)

      leiden_cluster_results_df = pd.DataFrame(leiden_cluster_results)
      print(leiden_cluster_results_df.head(10)) # To verify the data
```

```
      communityCount  modularity
0                67669    0.704205
```

Modularity measures the density of links inside communities compared to links between communities. A high modularity score suggests that the nodes within a cluster are more densely connected to each other than nodes outside the cluster.

Modularity: 0.704205 suggests a reasonably strong clustering, indicating that the Maven Central Repository has well-defined communities where dependencies are more prevalent within clusters than between them.

3.1.4 Write Community Assignments Back to the Database

```
[38]: # Write the communityId back to the database
      write_properties_query = f"""
      CALL gds.graph.writeNodeProperties('{graph_name}', ['communityId'])
      YIELD propertiesWritten
      """

      write_results = execute_query(write_properties_query)
      print(f"Node properties written back to the database:
      ↳{write_results[0]['propertiesWritten']}")
```

```
Node properties written back to the database: 15117217
```

3.1.5 Verify Community Assignments

```
[41]: # Verify the communityId property exists in the nodes
verify_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IS NOT NULL
RETURN n.communityId AS communityId, count(*) AS nodeCount
LIMIT 10
"""

verify_results = execute_query(verify_query)

# Print out a sample of the results
for result in verify_results:
    print(f"CommunityId: {result['communityId']}, Node Count:␣
↪{result['nodeCount']}")
```

```
CommunityId: 28940, Node Count: 1632903
CommunityId: 30270, Node Count: 1028568
CommunityId: 43407, Node Count: 66
CommunityId: 48568, Node Count: 1073498
CommunityId: 26959, Node Count: 1795221
CommunityId: 10862, Node Count: 372129
CommunityId: 13965, Node Count: 550821
CommunityId: 13026, Node Count: 4
CommunityId: 657, Node Count: 59604
CommunityId: 27287, Node Count: 128003
```

3.1.6 Get Properties Available in Database

```
[44]: # Query to get all node properties in the graph
all_properties_query = """
CALL db.schema.nodeTypeProperties()
YIELD nodeType, propertyName
RETURN nodeType, propertyName
ORDER BY nodeType, propertyName
"""

properties_results = execute_query(all_properties_query)

# Print out the node types and their properties
for result in properties_results:
    print(f"Node Type: {result['nodeType']}, Property Name:␣
↪{result['propertyName']}")
```

```
Node Type: :`AddedValue`, Property Name: id
Node Type: :`AddedValue`, Property Name: type
Node Type: :`AddedValue`, Property Name: value
Node Type: :`Artifact`, Property Name: communityId
Node Type: :`Artifact`, Property Name: found
Node Type: :`Artifact`, Property Name: id
```

Node Type: :`Release`, Property Name: communityId
Node Type: :`Release`, Property Name: id
Node Type: :`Release`, Property Name: timestamp
Node Type: :`Release`, Property Name: version

3.2 Analyze Top Clusters

3.2.1 Examine Cluster Sizes and Basic Statistics

Identify how large each cluster is and how they compare to another.
This provides context for their significance in the ecosystem.

```
[49]: # Query to get cluster sizes
cluster_sizes_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IS NOT NULL
RETURN n.communityId AS communityId, count(*) AS size
ORDER BY size DESC
LIMIT 10
"""

cluster_sizes = execute_query(cluster_sizes_query)
cluster_sizes_df = pd.DataFrame(cluster_sizes)
print("Top 10 Clusters by Size:")
print(cluster_sizes_df)
```

Top 10 Clusters by Size:

	communityId	size
0	26959	1795221
1	28940	1632903
2	29418	1293045
3	48568	1073498
4	30270	1028568
5	34416	775442
6	65609	613915
7	28947	561882
8	13965	550821
9	14097	458680

Create a Bar Chart to Display Information

```
[52]: # Create a bar chart
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 7))
plt.bar(cluster_sizes_df['communityId'].astype(str), cluster_sizes_df['size'],
        color='skyblue')
plt.xlabel('Community ID')
plt.ylabel('Cluster Size')
plt.title('Top 10 Clusters by Size in the Maven Central Dependency Graph')
plt.xticks(rotation=45) # Rotate x-axis labels for better readability
plt.tight_layout()     # Adjust layout to make room for labels
```

```
plt.show()
```


3.2.2 Analyze All Clusters

```
[55]: # Query to get cluster sizes
cluster_sizes_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IS NOT NULL
RETURN n.communityId AS communityId, count(*) AS size
ORDER BY size DESC
"""

cluster_sizes_all = execute_query(cluster_sizes_query)
cluster_sizes_all_df = pd.DataFrame(cluster_sizes_all)
print("All Clusters Sorted by Size, only show top few:")
print(cluster_sizes_all_df.head(20))
```

All Clusters Sorted by Size, only show top few:

	communityId	size
0	26959	1795221
1	28940	1632903
2	29418	1293045
3	48568	1073498
4	30270	1028568
5	34416	775442
6	65609	613915
7	28947	561882

8	13965	550821
9	14097	458680
10	17717	439791
11	10862	372129
12	10471	368422
13	31276	348112
14	21652	317599
15	29205	253813
16	35373	177326
17	67551	168704
18	28969	129070
19	27287	128003

Create a Scatter Plot to Show the Distribution of Cluster Sizes

```
[58]: # Sort the clusters by size in descending order for a more intuitive
      ↪ distribution plot
cluster_sizes_all_df = cluster_sizes_all_df.sort_values(by='size',
      ↪ ascending=False)

# Create a scatter plot with a logarithmic y-axis
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 7))
plt.scatter(range(len(cluster_sizes_all_df)), cluster_sizes_all_df['size'],
      ↪ color='blue', alpha=0.6)
plt.yscale('log') # Set the y-axis to a logarithmic scale
plt.xlabel('Cluster Index (Sorted by Size)')
plt.ylabel('Cluster Size (Log Scale)')
# plt.title('Distribution of Cluster Sizes in Maven Central (Logarithmic
      ↪ Scale)') # remove title for inclusion in paper
plt.tight_layout()

plt.savefig('cluster_size_distribution.pdf', bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
plt.close()
```


Use a Density Plot

```
[61]: # Create a histogram with a logarithmic scale
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 7))
plt.hist(cluster_sizes_all_df['size'], bins=100, color='blue', alpha=0.6)
plt.yscale('log')
plt.xlabel('Cluster Size')
plt.ylabel('Frequency (Log Scale)')
plt.title('Density of Cluster Sizes in Maven Central')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```


Display as a KDE Plot

```
[68]: plt.figure(figsize=(4,3))
sns.kdeplot(cluster_sizes_all_df['size'], log_scale=True, color='blue')
plt.xlabel('Cluster Size')
plt.ylabel('Density')
# plt.title('Kernel Density Estimate of Cluster Sizes')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('cluster_size_KDE.pdf', bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
```



```
[82]: # Plotting the KDE plot with a logarithmic x-axis
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))
sns.kdeplot(cluster_sizes_all_df['size'], color='blue')
plt.xscale('log') # Set x-axis to a logarithmic scale
plt.xlabel('Cluster Size (Log Scale)')
plt.ylabel('Density')
plt.title('Kernel Density Estimate of Cluster Sizes (Log Scale)')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```



```
[84]: # Plotting a histogram with a KDE overlay
plt.figure(figsize=(4, 3))
sns.histplot(cluster_sizes_all_df['size'], bins=50, color='lightblue',
             kde=True, log_scale=(True, False))
plt.xscale('log') # Use a logarithmic scale for the x-axis
plt.xlabel('Cluster Size (Log Scale)')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')
plt.title('Distribution of Cluster Sizes with KDE Overlay (Log Scale)')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.savefig('cluster_size_KDE_overlay.pdf', bbox_inches='tight')
plt.show()
```

Distribution of Cluster Sizes with KDE Overlay (Log Scale)


```
[90]: # Annotate the largest clusters
largest_clusters = cluster_sizes_all_df.sort_values(by='size', ascending=False).
    ↪head(5)

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))
sns.kdeplot(cluster_sizes_all_df['size'], color='blue')
plt.xscale('log')
plt.xlabel('Cluster Size (Log Scale)')
plt.ylabel('Density')
plt.title('Kernel Density Estimate of Cluster Sizes (Log Scale)')

# Add annotations
for index, row in largest_clusters.iterrows():
    plt.annotate(f"ID: {row['communityId']}\nSize: {row['size']}",
                xy=(row['size'], 0.02), # Adjust the y-value for visibility
                xytext=(row['size'], 0.1),
                arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->", color='black'),
                fontsize=8)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```


3.2.3 Find Top Cluster IDs

```
[73]: # Define N - number of top clusters to analyze
N = 20 # Adjust N based on what your system can handle

# Query to get top N clusters by size
top_clusters_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IS NOT NULL
RETURN n.communityId AS communityId, count(*) AS size
ORDER BY size DESC
LIMIT {N}
"""

top_clusters = execute_query(top_clusters_query)
top_cluster_ids = [row['communityId'] for row in top_clusters]
print(f"Top {N} clusters: {top_cluster_ids}")
```

Top 20 clusters: [26959, 28940, 29418, 48568, 30270, 34416, 65609, 28947, 13965, 14097, 17717, 10862, 10471, 31276, 21652, 29205, 35373, 67551, 28969, 27287]

3.2.4 Analyze Artifact Composition

Examine sample artifacts to infer the common themes or functionalities within each cluster.

```
[75]: # For each top cluster, sample artifacts
for cluster_id in top_cluster_ids:
    sample_artifacts_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId = {cluster_id}
RETURN labels(n) AS node_type, n.id AS name, n.version AS version
LIMIT 10
"""
    artifacts = execute_query(sample_artifacts_query)
    artifacts_df = pd.DataFrame(artifacts)
    print(f"Sample artifacts from Cluster {cluster_id}:")
    print(artifacts_df)
```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 26959:

	node_type	name	version
0	[Artifact]	com.lihaoyi:ammonite-shell_2.10.5	None
1	[Artifact]	com.codacy:codacy-engine-scala-seed_2.12	None
2	[Release]	com.codacy:codacy-engine-scala-seed_2.12:3.0.183	3.0.183
3	[Release]	com.lihaoyi:ammonite-shell_2.10.5:COMMIT-38f6574	COMMIT-38f6574
4	[Artifact]	io.janstenpickle:trace4cats-meta_2.13	None
5	[Release]	io.janstenpickle:trace4cats-meta_2.13:0.7.0+168-2ce97ef2	0.7.0+168-2ce97ef2
6	[Artifact]	dev.zio:zio-aws-resourcegroups_2.12	None
7	[Release]	dev.zio:zio-aws-resourcegroups_2.12:5.17.233.1	5.17.233.1
8	[Artifact]	org.hawkular.metrics:hawkular-metrics-load-tests	None
9	[Artifact]	ch.epfl.lamp:dotty-language-server_0.25	None

Sample artifacts from Cluster 28940:

	node_type	name	version
0	[Artifact]	com.splendo.kaluga:alerts-androidlib	None
1	[Release]	com.splendo.kaluga:alerts-androidlib:0.5.0	0.5.0
2	[Artifact]	io.github.agoraio-community:AgoraEduCore	None
3	[Release]	io.github.agoraio-community:AgoraEduCore:2.1.101	2.1.101
4	[Artifact]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32	None
5	[Release]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32:1.5.1	1.5.1
6	[Release]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32:1.5.4	1.5.4
7	[Release]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32:1.5.2	1.5.2
8	[Release]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32:1.5.0	1.5.0
9	[Release]	io.ktor:ktor-client-core-watchosarm32:1.5.3	1.5.3

Sample artifacts from Cluster 29418:

	node_type	name	version	
0	[Artifact]	org.apache.karaf.decanter.collector:org.apache.karaf.decanter.collector.snmp		None
1	[Release]	org.apache.karaf.decanter.collector:org.apache.karaf.decanter.collector.snmp:2.10.0	2.10.0	
2	[Artifact]	nz.ac.waikato.cms.weka:weka-stable		None
3	[Artifact]	org.kie.workbench:kie-wb-common-dev		None
4	[Release]	org.kie.workbench:kie-wb-common-dev:7.50.0.Final	7.50.0.Final	
5	[Artifact]	com.commercetools.sdk:commercetools-money		None
6	[Artifact]	jp.co.future:uroborosql		None
7	[Release]	com.commercetools.sdk:commercetools-money:10.0.0	10.0.0	
8	[Release]	jp.co.future:uroborosql:0.21.0	0.21.0	
9	[Release]	jp.co.future:uroborosql:0.21.1	0.21.1	

Sample artifacts from Cluster 48568:

	node_type	name	version
0	[Artifact]	io.projectreactor:reactor-scala-extensions_2.11	
			None
1	[Artifact]	org.grails:grails-datastore-simple	
			None
2	[Release]	org.grails:grails-datastore-simple:3.0.6.RELEASE	3.0.6.RELEASE
3	[Release]	io.projectreactor:reactor-scala-extensions_2.11:0.4.0	0.4.0
4	[Release]	io.projectreactor:reactor-scala-extensions_2.11:0.4.6	0.4.6
5	[Release]	io.projectreactor:reactor-scala-extensions_2.11:0.4.1	0.4.1
6	[Release]	io.projectreactor:reactor-scala-extensions_2.11:0.4.7	0.4.7
7	[Artifact]	org.apache.camel.springboot:camel-file-watch-starter	
			None
8	[Release]	org.apache.camel.springboot:camel-file-watch-starter:3.18.1	3.18.1
9	[Release]	org.apache.camel.springboot:camel-file-watch-starter:3.18.0	3.18.0

Sample artifacts from Cluster 30270:

```

node_type
name version
0 [Artifact]
org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.mgt.core
None
1 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.111 5.20.111
2 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.113 5.20.113
3 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.112 5.20.112
4 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.115 5.20.115
5 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.114 5.20.114
6 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.110 5.20.110
7 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.118 5.20.118
8 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.119 5.20.119
9 [Release] org.wso2.carbon.identity.framework:org.wso2.carbon.identity.cors.
mgt.core:5.20.117 5.20.117

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 34416:

```

node_type
name version
0 [Artifact] io.github.expatiat.jambalaya:jambalaya-checks-
jooq None
1 [Release] io.github.expatiat.jambalaya:jambalaya-checks-
jooq:0.2.0 0.2.0
2 [Artifact] org.opendaylight.mdsal.model:ietf-
network-2015-06-08 None
3 [Release] org.opendaylight.mdsal.model:ietf-network-2015-06-08:1.1.2-Boron-
SR2 1.1.2-Boron-SR2
4 [Artifact] io.jooby:jooby-
test None
5 [Artifact] com.guicedee.services:commons-
xmlbeans None
6 [Release] com.guicedee.services:commons-
xmlbeans:1.0.19.0-jre14 1.0.19.0-jre14
7 [Release] com.guicedee.services:commons-
xmlbeans:1.0.19.0-jre15 1.0.19.0-jre15
8 [Release] io.vertigo:vertigo-spring-
connector:3.0.0-RC 3.0.0-RC
9 [Artifact] com.sap.cloud.sdk.frameworks:javaee None

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 65609:

```

node_type name

```

```

version
0 [Artifact]          com.google.cloud:google-cloud-errorreporting
None
1 [Release]  com.google.cloud:google-cloud-errorreporting:0.122.5-beta
0.122.5-beta
2 [Artifact]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module
None
3 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.0
0.11.0
4 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.3
0.11.3
5 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.4
0.11.4
6 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.2
0.11.2
7 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.1
0.11.1
8 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.5
0.11.5
9 [Release]          ru.tinkoff.kora:opentelemetry-module:0.11.6
0.11.6

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 28947:

```

      node_type          name          version
0 [Artifact]          org.apache.flink:flink-test-utils          None
1 [Release]          org.apache.flink:flink-test-utils:1.17.0    1.17.0
2 [Release]          org.apache.flink:flink-test-utils:1.17.1    1.17.1
3 [Artifact]          org.apache.seatunnel:connector-sentry          None
4 [Release]  org.apache.seatunnel:connector-sentry:2.3.0-beta    2.3.0-beta
5 [Release]          org.graylog2:graylog2-parent:2.0.0-alpha.2  2.0.0-alpha.2
6 [Release]          org.graylog2:graylog2-parent:2.0.0-alpha.1  2.0.0-alpha.1
7 [Release]          org.graylog2:graylog2-parent:2.0.0-alpha.4  2.0.0-alpha.4
8 [Release]          org.graylog2:graylog2-parent:2.0.0-alpha.5  2.0.0-alpha.5
9 [Release]          org.graylog2:graylog2-parent:2.0.0-alpha.3  2.0.0-alpha.3

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 13965:

```

      node_type          name          version
name version
0 [Artifact]          org.ops4j.pax.exam.samples:pax-exam-
sample7-service    None
1 [Release]          org.ops4j.pax.exam.samples:pax-exam-
sample7-service:4.12.0  4.12.0
2 [Artifact]          com.liferay:com.liferay.portal.security.service.access.policy.api    None
3 [Release]          com.liferay:com.liferay.portal.security.service.access.policy.api:6.3.0    6.3.0
4 [Artifact]          org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module    None
5 [Release]          org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module:8.0.1    8.0.1

```

```

6 [Release] org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module:8.0.0 8.0.0
7 [Release] org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module:8.0.2 8.0.2
8 [Release] org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module:8.0.3 8.0.3
9 [Release] org.finos.symphony.toolkit:jackson-quickfix-
module:8.0.4 8.0.4

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 14097:

```

node_type name
version
0 [Artifact] uk.co.automatictester:lightning
None
1 [Release] uk.co.automatictester:lightning:1.0.0
1.0.0
2 [Artifact] software.amazon.awscdk:ecs
None
3 [Release] software.amazon.awscdk:ecs:0.38.0.DEVPREVIEW
0.38.0.DEVPREVIEW
4 [Artifact] software.amazon.awscdk:cloud9-alpha
None
5 [Artifact] org.apache.skywalking:apm-nutz-http-1.x-plugin
None
6 [Release] software.amazon.awscdk:cloud9-alpha:2.43.1-alpha.0
2.43.1-alpha.0
7 [Release] org.apache.skywalking:apm-nutz-http-1.x-plugin:8.6.0
8.6.0
8 [Artifact] io.streamnative:pulsar-io-jdbc-mariadb
None
9 [Release] io.streamnative:pulsar-io-jdbc-mariadb:2.9.0-rc-202106222205
2.9.0-rc-202106222205

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 17717:

```

node_type name version
0 [Artifact] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch None
1 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.400 1.11.400
2 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.401 1.11.401
3 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.402 1.11.402
4 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.403 1.11.403
5 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.404 1.11.404
6 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.407 1.11.407
7 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.405 1.11.405
8 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.408 1.11.408
9 [Release] com.amazonaws:aws-java-sdk-elasticsearch:1.11.406 1.11.406

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 10862:

```

node_type name
version
0 [Artifact] org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro
None

```

```

1  [Release]  org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro:1.0.2
1.0.2
2  [Release]  org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro:1.0.0
1.0.0
3  [Release]  org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro:1.0.1
1.0.1
4  [Release]  org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro:1.0.3
1.0.3
5  [Release]  org.bedework.deploy:bw-wfmodules-calendar-engine-core-ro:1.0.4
1.0.4
6  [Artifact]  io.vertigo:vertigo-spring-connector
None
7  [Artifact]  org.apache.iceberg:iceberg-common
None
8  [Release]  org.apache.iceberg:iceberg-common:1.2.0
1.2.0
9  [Release]  org.apache.iceberg:iceberg-common:1.2.1
1.2.1
Sample artifacts from Cluster 10471:
  node_type          name
version
0  [Artifact]  org.teiid:spring-data-hsql
None
1  [Artifact]  org.jboss.weld:weld-core-parent
None
2  [Release]  org.jboss.weld:weld-core-parent:5.1.1.Final
5.1.1.Final
3  [Release]  org.teiid:spring-data-hsql:1.7.2
1.7.2
4  [Release]  org.teiid:spring-data-hsql:1.7.1
1.7.1
5  [Artifact]  io.quarkus:quarkus-bootstrap-gradle-resolver
None
6  [Release]  io.quarkus:quarkus-bootstrap-gradle-resolver:2.8.2.Final
2.8.2.Final
7  [Artifact]  org.alfasoftware:morf-postgresql
None
8  [Release]  org.alfasoftware:morf-postgresql:2.8.0
2.8.0
9  [Release]  org.alfasoftware:morf-postgresql:2.8.1
2.8.1
Sample artifacts from Cluster 31276:
  node_type          name          version
0  [Artifact]  io.quarkus:quarkus-
vertx-deployment  None
1  [Release]  io.quarkus:quarkus-vertx-
deployment:2.9.2.Final  2.9.2.Final

```

```

2 [Artifact]
org.projectnessie:nessie-ui          None
3 [Artifact]          io.eventuate.local.java:eventuate-local-java-jdbc-
tests-common          None
4 [Release]
org.projectnessie:nessie-ui:0.27.0    0.27.0
5 [Release] io.eventuate.local.java:eventuate-local-java-jdbc-tests-
common:0.36.0.RELEASE 0.36.0.RELEASE
6 [Artifact]          org.keycloak:keycloak-quarkus-
server-deployment      None
7 [Release]          org.keycloak:keycloak-quarkus-server-
deployment:18.0.0      18.0.0
8 [Release]          org.keycloak:keycloak-quarkus-server-
deployment:18.0.1      18.0.1
9 [Release]          org.keycloak:keycloak-quarkus-server-
deployment:18.0.2      18.0.2

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 21652:

```

node_type          name
version
0 [Artifact]          org.apache.archiva:archiva-docs
None
1 [Release]          org.apache.archiva:archiva-docs:1.1.2
1.1.2
2 [Release]          org.apache.archiva:archiva-docs:1.1.1
1.1.1
3 [Release]          org.apache.archiva:archiva-docs:1.1.3
1.1.3
4 [Release]          org.apache.archiva:archiva-docs:1.1.4
1.1.4
5 [Artifact]          com.cognitect.aws:resourcegroupstaggingapi
None
6 [Release] com.cognitect.aws:resourcegroupstaggingapi:807.2.729.0
807.2.729.0
7 [Artifact]          marmalade:marmalade-tags-inertDoco
None
8 [Release]          marmalade:marmalade-tags-inertDoco:1.0
1.0
9 [Artifact] app.myoss.cloud.maven.plugins:archetypes-maven-plugin
None

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 29205:

```

node_type          name          version
0 [Artifact]          com.softwaremill.sttp.tapir:tapir-openapi-
circe_3          None
1 [Release]          com.softwaremill.sttp.tapir:tapir-openapi-
circe_3:0.20.0-M10 0.20.0-M10
2 [Artifact]          org.scala-
lang:scala3-library_3          None

```

```

3 [Artifact] org.typelevel:cats-effect-kernel-
testkit_native0.4_3 None
4 [Artifact] io.github.vigoo:zio-aws-
alexaforbusiness_3 None
5 [Release] org.typelevel:cats-effect-kernel-
testkit_native0.4_3:3.3.14-2-0972521 3.3.14-2-0972521
6 [Release] io.github.vigoo:zio-aws-
alexaforbusiness_3:3.17.11.1 3.17.11.1
7 [Artifact] dev.zio:zio-aws-
rekognition_3 None
8 [Release] dev.zio:zio-aws-
rekognition_3:5.20.22.1 5.20.22.1
9 [Release] dev.zio:zio-aws-
rekognition_3:5.20.22.2 5.20.22.2
Sample artifacts from Cluster 35373:

```

```

node_type name
version
0 [Artifact] io.ceresdb:ceresdb-sql-javacc
None
1 [Release] io.ceresdb:ceresdb-sql-javacc:1.0.0-alpha
1.0.0-alpha
2 [Release] io.netty:netty-all:4.1.23.Final
4.1.23.Final
3 [Artifact] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api
None
4 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.5
9.11.5
5 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.6
9.11.6
6 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.4
9.11.4
7 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.2
9.11.2
8 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.3
9.11.3
9 [Release] org.xwiki.commons:xwiki-commons-component-api:9.11.1
9.11.1

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 67551:

```

node_type name version
0 [Artifact] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
vault None
1 [Release] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
vault:v1-rev20190320-1.26.0 v1-rev20190320-1.26.0
2 [Artifact] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
datastore None
3 [Release] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
datastore:v1beta1-rev67-1.18.0-rc v1beta1-rev67-1.18.0-rc

```

```

4 [Artifact] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
cloudbuild None
5 [Release] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
cloudbuild:v1-rev132-1.18.0-rc v1-rev132-1.18.0-rc
6 [Artifact] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
lifesciences None
7 [Release] com.google.apis:google-api-services-lifesciences:v2beta-
rev18-1.25.0 v2beta-rev18-1.25.0
8 [Artifact] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
people None
9 [Release] com.google.apis:google-api-services-
people:v1-rev424-1.24.1 v1-rev424-1.24.1

```

Sample artifacts from Cluster 28969:

	node_type	name	version
0	[Artifact]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client	None
1	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.10	0.1.10
2	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.16	0.1.16
3	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.15	0.1.15
4	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.14	0.1.14
5	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.12	0.1.12
6	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.11	0.1.11
7	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.13	0.1.13
8	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.17	0.1.17
9	[Release]	com.netflix.metacat:metacat-client:0.1.18	0.1.18

Sample artifacts from Cluster 27287:

	node_type	name	version
0	[Artifact]	org.guvnor:guvnor- inbox-client	None
1	[Release]	org.guvnor:guvnor-inbox- client:6.4.0.Beta2	6.4.0.Beta2
2	[Release]	org.guvnor:guvnor-inbox- client:6.4.0.Beta1	6.4.0.Beta1
3	[Artifact]	org.drools:drools-wb- distribution-wars	None
4	[Release]	org.drools:drools-wb-distribution- wars:6.0.0.Beta4	6.0.0.Beta4
5	[Release]	org.drools:drools-wb-distribution- wars:6.0.0.Beta3	6.0.0.Beta3
6	[Release]	org.drools:drools-wb-distribution- wars:6.0.0.Beta5	6.0.0.Beta5
7	[Artifact]	org.kie:kie-internal	None
8	[Artifact]	org.kie.workbench.screens:kie-wb-common-datasource- mgmt-client	None
9	[Release]	org.kie.workbench.screens:kie-wb-common-datasource- client:7.74.0.Final	7.74.0.Final

3.2.5 Analyze Inter-Cluster Relationships

- Identify which clusters have the most dependencies between them
- Understand the strength and directionality of the interactions.

```
[77]: # Query to analyze inter-cluster relationships
inter_cluster_query = f"""
MATCH (a)-[r]->(b)
WHERE a.communityId <> b.communityId
RETURN a.communityId AS sourceCluster, b.communityId AS targetCluster, count(*)
↳AS connections
ORDER BY connections DESC
LIMIT 10
"""

inter_cluster_connections = execute_query(inter_cluster_query)
inter_cluster_df = pd.DataFrame(inter_cluster_connections)
print("Top 10 Inter-Cluster Connections:")
print(inter_cluster_df)
```

Top 10 Inter-Cluster Connections:

	sourceCluster	targetCluster	connections
0	48568	29418	1791786
1	29418	48568	1447774
2	34416	29418	837511
3	34416	28947	711388
4	29418	28947	699461
5	26959	29418	502251
6	13965	29418	451899
7	30270	29418	451654
8	65609	29418	450349
9	48568	28947	450185

3.2.6 Export Data for Visualization

```
[80]: # Convert cluster IDs to a string for Cypher query
cluster_ids_string = ', '.join(map(str, top_cluster_ids))

# Query to get nodes in top clusters
nodes_export_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IN [{cluster_ids_string}]
RETURN id(n) AS nodeId, labels(n) AS labels, n.id AS name, n.communityId AS
↳communityId
"""

nodes = execute_query(nodes_export_query)
nodes_df = pd.DataFrame(nodes)
print(f"Exported {len(nodes_df)} nodes from top {N} clusters.")
```

Exported 12486944 nodes from top 20 clusters.

```
[86]: # Save to JSON
nodes_df.to_json('nodes_top_clusters.json', orient='records', lines=False)
print("Nodes have been saved to 'nodes_top_clusters.json'.")
```

Nodes have been saved to 'nodes_top_clusters.json'.

3.2.7 Explore Bidirectional Connections

```
[88]: # Query to identify bidirectional inter-cluster connections
bidirectional_query = f"""
MATCH (a)-[r1]->(b), (b)-[r2]->(a)
WHERE a.communityId <> b.communityId
RETURN a.communityId AS sourceCluster, b.communityId AS targetCluster,
       count(r1) + count(r2) AS totalConnections
ORDER BY totalConnections DESC
LIMIT 10
"""

bidirectional_connections = execute_query(bidirectional_query)
bidirectional_df = pd.DataFrame(bidirectional_connections)
print("Top 10 Bidirectional Inter-Cluster Connections:")
print(bidirectional_df)
```

Top 10 Bidirectional Inter-Cluster Connections:

	sourceCluster	targetCluster	totalConnections
0	26959	48568	56
1	48568	26959	56
2	10862	28947	34
3	28947	10862	34
4	29418	35373	18
5	35373	29418	18
6	48568	28940	10
7	28940	48568	10
8	29418	65609	8
9	65609	29418	8

3.2.8 Investigate Inter-Cluster Interactions

Visualize Inter-Cluster Relationships

```
[92]: # Create a directed graph
G = nx.DiGraph()

# Add a subset of nodes and edges for clarity
for index, row in inter_cluster_df.iterrows():
    G.add_edge(row['sourceCluster'], row['targetCluster'],
               weight=row['connections'])

# Use Kamada-Kawai layout for a more evenly distributed graph
```

```

pos = nx.kamada_kawai_layout(G)

# Scale node sizes by the degree of each node
node_sizes = [G.degree(node) * 50 for node in G.nodes()]

# Draw the graph with customized settings
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos, node_size=node_sizes, node_color='lightblue',
    ↪alpha=0.8)
nx.draw_networkx_edges(G, pos, edgelist=G.edges(), width=2, edge_color='gray',
    ↪alpha=0.6)
nx.draw_networkx_labels(G, pos, font_size=8, font_color='black')

plt.title("Enhanced Inter-Cluster Connections in Maven Central")
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```


Heatmap for Connection Strengths

```

[94]: # Pivot the DataFrame to create a matrix for the heatmap
heatmap_data = inter_cluster_df.pivot(index="sourceCluster",
    ↪columns="targetCluster", values="connections")

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))
sns.heatmap(heatmap_data, cmap="Blues", annot=True, fmt=".0f", linewidths=0.5)
plt.title("Heatmap of Key Inter-Cluster Connection Strengths")
plt.xlabel("Target Cluster")
plt.ylabel("Source Cluster")
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```


Identify Bridge Nodes - Releases

```

[96]: # Query to find bridge nodes (artifacts/release nodes connecting clusters)
bridge_nodes_query = f"""
MATCH (a)-[r:dependency]->(b)
WHERE a.communityId IS NOT NULL AND b.communityId IS NOT NULL AND a.communityId <
  <> b.communityId
RETURN a.id AS bridgeRelease, a.communityId AS sourceCluster, b.communityId AS <
  <targetCluster, count(r) AS connectionCount

```

```

ORDER BY connectionCount DESC
LIMIT 100
"""

# Execute the query
bridge_nodes = execute_query(bridge_nodes_query)
bridge_nodes_df = pd.DataFrame(bridge_nodes)

# Display the results
print("Top 30 Bridge Nodes Between Clusters:")
print(bridge_nodes_df)

```

Top 30 Bridge Nodes Between Clusters:

sourceCluster	targetCluster	connectionCount	bridgeRelease
0			org.apache.camel:apache-camel:3.0.0
48568	13965	311	
1			org.apache.camel:apache-camel:3.0.1
48568	13965	311	
2			io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-4307e
10862	13965	121	
3			io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-4307a
10862	13965	121	
4			io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-43073
10862	13965	121	
..			...
95			it.agilelab:wasp-model_2.11:2.32.0-cdp717
10862	26959	62	
96	org.ops4j.pax.web.itest.container:pax-web-itest-container-jetty:7.4.1		
65609	13965	62	
97	org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.28.130		
29418	30270	62	
98	org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.28.69		
29418	30270	62	
99	org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.29.22		
29418	30270	62	

[100 rows x 4 columns]

Identify Bridge Nodes - Artifacts

```

[98]: # Extract the artifact name from the bridgeRelease string
bridge_nodes_df['artifactId'] = bridge_nodes_df['bridgeRelease'].str.split(':').
↳str[0]

# Display the updated DataFrame
print("Updated DataFrame with Artifact Names:")

```

```
print(bridge_nodes_df[['bridgeRelease', 'artifactId']])
```

Updated DataFrame with Artifact Names:

```
                                bridgeRelease
artifactId
0                                org.apache.camel:apache-camel:3.0.0
org.apache.camel
1                                org.apache.camel:apache-camel:3.0.1
org.apache.camel
2                                io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-4307e
io.hyte.platform
3                                io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-4307a
io.hyte.platform
4                                io.hyte.platform:repo:4.3.7.hyte-43073
io.hyte.platform
..                                ...
...
95                               it.agilelab:wasp-model_2.11:2.32.0-cdp717
it.agilelab
96  org.ops4j.pax.web.itest.container:pax-web-itest-container-jetty:7.4.1
org.ops4j.pax.web.itest.container
97          org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.28.130
org.wso2.carbon.apimgt
98          org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.28.69
org.wso2.carbon.apimgt
99          org.wso2.carbon.apimgt:org.wso2.carbon.apimgt.impl:9.29.22
org.wso2.carbon.apimgt
```

[100 rows x 2 columns]

```
[199]: # Extract unique artifact names
unique_artifacts = bridge_nodes_df['artifactId'].unique()

# Display the unique artifacts
print("Unique Artifacts:")
print(unique_artifacts)
```

Unique Artifacts:

```
['org.apache.camel' 'org.opendaylight.controller'
 'org.ops4j.pax.web.itest' 'io.hyte.platform' 'org.springframework.boot'
 'it.agilelab' 'org.ops4j.pax.web.itest.container']
```

3.2.9 Analyzing Dependency Depth Within Clusters

Find the **depth of dependencies** within each cluster.

This query checks how deep the dependency chains are within a cluster by identifying how many layers of dependencies exist between artifacts and releases in the same cluster.

It looks for paths where one node depends on another, then counts how many dependencies exist along these paths.

```
[101]: # Define the query to get the depth of dependencies within each cluster
dependency_depth_query = f"""
MATCH (a)-[r:dependency*]->(b)
WHERE a.communityId = b.communityId
RETURN a.communityId AS communityId, count(r) AS depth
ORDER BY depth DESC
LIMIT 10
"""

# Execute the query
dependency_depths = execute_query(dependency_depth_query)
dependency_depths_df = pd.DataFrame(dependency_depths)

# Display the results
print("Top 10 Clusters by Dependency Depth:")
print(dependency_depths_df)
```

Top 10 Clusters by Dependency Depth:

	communityId	depth
0	48568	12861797
1	28947	10854528
2	26959	9834289
3	28940	9260035
4	29418	7225837
5	30270	5809257
6	34416	4762365
7	65609	4384609
8	14097	2613033
9	10471	2368639

Deeper dependency chains suggest that the cluster is more complex, with artifacts depending on multiple layers of other artifacts.

Complex clusters can be harder to manage, update, or refactor since changes to one artifact might ripple through the entire chain of dependencies, increasing maintenance cost and risks.

3.2.10 Analyzing Age of Artifacts in Clusters

Older dependencies could signal technical debt or clusters at risk for security vulnerabilities. Analyzing the age of artifacts within a cluster gives insight into how frequently the dependencies are updated.

```
[104]: # Define the query to get the age of artifacts in each top cluster
artifact_age_query = f"""
MATCH (n)
WHERE n.communityId IN {top_cluster_ids}
RETURN n.communityId AS communityId, n.id AS artifact_id, n.timestamp AS_
↪release_date
```

```

ORDER BY n.timestamp ASC
LIMIT 100
"""

# Execute the query
artifact_ages = execute_query(artifact_age_query)
artifact_ages_df = pd.DataFrame(artifact_ages)

# Convert the timestamp into readable dates if necessary
artifact_ages_df['release_date'] = pd.
↳to_datetime(artifact_ages_df['release_date'], unit='ms')

# Display the results
print("Artifact ages in top clusters:")
print(artifact_ages_df.head(10))

```

Artifact ages in top clusters:

	communityId	artifact_id	release_date
0	21652	org.jdom:jaxen-core:1.0-FCS	2002-05-15 04:32:34
1	21652	org.jdom:saxpath:1.0-FCS	2002-05-15 04:32:34
2	29418	com.toedter:jcalendar:1.1.4	2002-07-17 22:45:02
3	30270	xalan:xalan:2.5.D1	2003-03-02 20:33:39
4	48568	xmlpull:xmlpull:1.1.3.1	2003-06-17 00:03:58
5	14097	com.micheldalal:x10:1.0.1	2003-10-21 14:31:42
6	29418	com.incors.plaf:kunststoff:2.0.2	2004-07-07 01:00:56
7	21652	org.jdom:jaxen-jdom:1.0-FCS	2004-09-03 06:14:48
8	21652	com.caucho:resin:3.0.9	2004-10-02 22:52:42
9	21652	sslext:sslext:1.2-0	2004-10-03 20:10:42

3.3 Close Projected Graph

```
[107]: with driver.session() as session:
        session.run("CALL gds.graph.drop('mavenGraph')")
```

```
[ ]:
```